

Greener Journal of Life Sciences

Distribution and Abundance of the Mantis Shrimp *Squilla mantis* (Crustacea: Stomatopoda) in Tunisian Waters: Gulfs of Tunis, Hammamet and Gabes

By

**Sami Mili
Rym Ennouri
Othman Jarbouï
Hechmi Missaoui**

Research Article

Distribution and Abundance of the Mantis Shrimp *Squilla mantis* (Crustacea: Stomatopoda) in Tunisian Waters: Gulfs of Tunis, Hammamet and Gabes

Sami Mili^{1,2*}, Rym Ennouri², Othman Jarboui² and Hechmi Missaoui³

¹Unité Exploitation des milieux aquatiques, Institut Supérieur de Pêche et d'Aquaculture de Bizerte, BP 15, 7080 Menzel Jemil, Tunisia.

²Institut National des Sciences et Technologies de la Mer. 28, Rue 2 Mars 1934, 2025 Salammbô, Tunisia.

³Direction Générale de la pêche et de l'Aquaculture. 32, Rue Alain Savary, Tunis 1002, Tunisia.

*Corresponding Author's Email: sami_mili@yahoo.fr

ABSTRACT

The mantis shrimp *Squilla mantis* is a crustacean Stomatopod of the family of the Squillidae. This specie is found in high densities in areas with suitable burrowing substrates in the Mediterranean Sea. The objectives of the present study were to characterize the distribution and the abundance of the spot-tail mantis shrimp caught in Tunisian waters. The Spot-tail mantis shrimp is exploited in this area and it is still considered as a bycatch, but its abundance makes it important for fisheries. Information about distribution, abundance and size composition of the *Squilla mantis* were obtained from trawl surveys, carried out in the Tunisian Gulfs monthly for a period of two years. A total of 643 hauls were made and 22,878 specimens were captured. This study shows that this mantis shrimp is very abundant in the Tunisian waters, especially in the Gulf of Tunis, Hammamet and Gabes. *S. mantis* has a wide geographic distribution, since it was collected in all the major areas investigated, but differences were highlighted among the geographic sectors sampled. Maximum abundances occur shallower than 50 m depth. The values of the catches vary seasonally, the highest of which occurring in summer and autumn. Adults disappeared from the population during winter whereas females do not exit their burrow during incubation. The variability of the catches is due to the effect of several factors such as the effect of month, season, depth, hour, luminosity, weather... This specie is more closely related to crustaceans, cephalopods and benthic fish's. According to the depth, no variation in length distributions of *Squilla mantis* is observed. The fact that egg-bearing females do not exit their burrow during incubation makes the catch ability lower during day-time. Trawling as well is not permitted shallower than 50 m in the Tunisian waters which may protect these species from fishing.

Keywords: *Squilla mantis*, distribution, abundance, environmental factors, trawl survey, Tunisian Gulfs.

INTRODUCTION

Fishery of the Spot-tail Mantis Shrimp (Fig.1), *Squilla mantis* (L., 1758) is found in the Mediterranean waters and in the adjacent Atlantic where this species has been reported from the Gulf of Cadiz and from the Canary Islands and Madeira, its southernmost distribution being Angola (Maynou et al. 2005). It is the only stomatopod crustacean commercially exploited in the Mediterranean and it is regularly found in the fish markets of Spain, Italy, Egypt, France and Morocco (Abelló and Martín, 1993). This Mantis Shrimp is found in high densities in areas with suitable burrowing substrates: fine sand and sandy mud, especially where the influence of river run-off is important (Atkinson et al., 1997). This species of Stomatopod is very abundant in the Tunisian coasts especially in the Gulfs of Gabes, Hammamet and Tunis (Mili et al., 2008). *Squilla mantis* is a species which has little economic importance in the Tunisian market, but its abundance in this area makes it a relatively important species for fisheries. It is a strongly sedentary species and the seasonal trends appearing in catches are not so much due to temporal changes in distribution caused by the limited migratory habit, as to its reproductive and burrowing behaviour, as linked to recruitment patterns. In the Tunisian Gulfs (Fig. 2), fishing is a well-developed activity characterized by high diversity in both target species and fishing gear used. Demersal catches are relatively important especially for the cuttlefish and the shrimps in Tunisians waters. *S. mantis* is one of the most dominant species in the demersal crustacean's fauna of the Tunisian gulfs (Mili et al., 2013). The importance attached to this resource is due to its high densities rather than to its market value. This species is subject to intense fishing activity carried out mainly by various gears such as trawl, baited traps, trammel nets and grill nets.

In the Gulf of Gabes, Hammamet and Tunis, multi-species are bottom trawl fishery. The Mantis Shrimp is usually an important by-catch of the fishing activity of the shrimps carried out on the continental shelf, from 30 to 60 m depth. The gear used is a common trawl net with large but flat mouth, heavily rigged, made of panels with decreasing meshes, and fitted to a cod-end of 38-40mm stretched mesh size (M'rabet, 1995). Catches of *Squilla mantis* are well documented from FAO statistics (Maynou *et al.*, 2005), but only for the north of the Mediterranean Sea. Despite this great fishing interest, studies defining distribution and abundance of stocks are still lacking in the Tunisian coasts. The present paper aims at contributing to the distribution, abundance and effects of specializations and considering to the environmental factors in the catches of *Squilla mantis* collected by means of professional trawl surveys carried out with a common methodology in a wide area of the Tunisian Gulfs: Gabes, Hammamet and Tunis.

Figure 1: The Spot-tail Mantis Shrimp *Squilla mantis* (L., 1758).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sampling

Twenty four monthly bottom trawl surveys were mainly aimed to obtain an estimate of the abundance indices for a series of demersal target species. They were carried out from January 2005 to December 2005 in the Gulf of Gabes and Hammamet (Fig. 3 & 4). Data on trawling in the Gulf of Tunis was collected in 2005 during the fisheries programme of monitoring and management in this area (Fig. 5). A total of 643 hauls were made in the depth range 10-180m, by means of standard trawl used in the Gulf of Gabes, Hammamet and Tunis to catch demersal resources having a cod-end mesh opening of 20mm. Selection of sampling station was randomly done while trying to cover all the bathymetric layers. Specimens were counted, weighed, measured (Total length, cephalothoraxes length) sexed and assigned.

Figure 2: Map of the Tunisian coast showing sampling areas (Gulf of Tunis, Hammamet and Gabes)

DATA ANALYSIS

The weight of the individuals captured per hour of trawling was calculated to provide an estimate of the abundance of the spot-tail Mantis Shrimp. For each haul, the hourly yields ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) were calculated to provide an estimate of the abundance and the distribution of the species. The cartography of distribution and abundance of this species is realised with ARCGIS 3.2. In order to examine the effect of several factors such as: month, season, hour, depth, weather, and lunar cycle on the catches, one-way ANOVA was used. The interaction between these factors influencing the quantity of *S. Mantis* captured was evaluated using two-way ANOVA and post hoc contrast analyses (Zar, 1984). Statistical analyses were performed with the package STATISTICA (release 8).

Figure 3: Position of trawls made in the Gulf of Gabes (2005).

Figure 4: Position of trawls made in the Gulf of Hammamet (2006).

Figure 5: Position of trawls made in the Gulf of Tunis (2003).

RESULTS

Trawl Surveys Analysis

During the different hauls made, catches of commercial species were accompanied by significant amounts of *S. mantis*. It should be noted that fisheries in the Gulfs of Gabes and Hammamet target mainly prawn. The qualitative study of landings and discards in the Tunisian Gulfs showed that the main commercial species landed are *Penaeus kerathurus* and *Metapenaeus monoceros* associated to *Boops boops*, *Mullus barbatus*, *Mullus surmuletus*, *Litognathus mormyrus*, *Merluccius merluccius*, *Diplodus sargus*, *Solea aegyptica*, *Liza aurata*, *Diplodus annularis*, *Raja sp.*, *Pagellus erythrinus*, *Pagrus coeruleostictus*, *Sepia officinalis* and *Sparus aurata*.

The discard is composed mainly by *Gobius niger*, *Serranus hepatus*, *Engraulis encrasicolus*, *Sardinia pilchardus*, *Trachurus mediterraneus*, *Citharus linguatula*, *Trachypenaeus curvirostris* and crabs. This discard is associated to a rich benthic fauna belonging to different ecological groups such as echinoderms, sponges, algae, seagrass, polychaetes, sponges and shell.

The presence of mantis shrimps in the catch is usually accompanied with crustaceans especially shrimp. This observation allows deducing that these species use the same seabed. The analysis of the mantis CPUE ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) compared to those of *Penaeus keratherus*, *Metapenaeus monoseros*, as well as of cephalopods and demersal fish's, showed that there is a strong link between crustaceans. The dendrogram (Fig. 6) points that *Squilla mantis* is strongly interconnected with the group of shrimp. The spot-tail mantis shrimp is linked primarily to a *P. keratherus* with a bond distance of 95% and subsequently to *M. monoseros*. The degree of binding of the mantis is more important with cephalopods (95.5%) compared to the benthic fishes which is about 93%. This link can be explained by trophic reason or requirement of a soft seabed habitat. This result indicates that this species is strongly related to crustaceans and it is very dependent to the bottom sediment.

Figure 6: Relationship between *S. mantis* and species caught in Tunisian Gulfs.

The Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted to determine the similarities between the species captured in the Gulf of Tunis, Hammamet and Gabes (Fig. 7). Abundances found, expressed in hourly output for different groups of species can be analyzed in relation with two main axes. The component 1 and 2 represents 56.84% of the total variance. The first component contributes with 30.44% of the variance and it is characterized by a positive contribution with benthic fish and cephalopods and with a negative contribution for crustaceans and *Squilla mantis*. The factor 2 contributes with 26.4% of the total variance and shows a positive correlation with *S. mantis* and crustaceans. According to the ACP, the groups of species analyzed can be classified in two groups. The first one includes *S. mantis* and crustaceans and has a positive correlation with the factor 2. The second group, composed by demersal fish and cephalopods has a positive correlation with factor 1.

Figure 7: Principal Component Analysis (PCA) applied to species caught in Tunisian Gulfs.

LENGTH DISTRIBUTION

A total of 8770 males and 7790 females were captured and measured in the Gulf of Gabes, 1404 females and 1620 males in the Gulf of Hammamet and 1726 males and 1564 females in the Gulf of Tunis. The details on numbers of individuals captured by sex and area are summarized in Table 1.

	Sex	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Gulf of Tunis	♀	148	180	146	88	113	144	140	100	108	128	132	137
	♂	159	156	74	162	138	186	164	153	107	154	139	134
	♀+♂	307	336	220	250	251	330	304	253	215	282	271	271
Gulf of Hammamet	♀	159	127	115	65	64	105	152	99	148	140	113	117
	♂	101	94	165	153	183	135	148	146	144	110	113	128
	♀+♂	260	221	280	218	247	240	300	245	292	250	226	245
Gulf of Gabès	♀	752	276	242	251	225	598	863	1022	799	810	616	1345
	♂	1537	573	602	803	1054	1421	1617	2184	1586	1618	1132	2442
	♀+♂	2289	849	844	1054	1279	2019	2480	3206	2385	2428	1748	3787

The variation in average size of the mantis shrimp captured according to depth indicates that there is no direct relationship between these parameters (Fig. 8). The following figure shows that *S. mantis* is abundant in the bathymetric slice from 15 to 45 m. The specimens having large sizes are lightly dominant between 20 and 25 m. It can be explained by the gathering of adults during the reproductive period in this range of depth. Generally, no correlation between size distributions and depth is observed.

Figure 8: Relationship between depth and size of *S. mantis*.

ABUNDANCE INDICES

Squilla mantis was distributed along all Tunisian Gulfs, though in a discontinuous way. The observation from the trawls survey showed a large heterogeneity in the catches of this species. The maximal hourly yield is estimated to reach 6.6 kg.h^{-1} , 5 kg.h^{-1} and 3.5 kg.h^{-1} respectively in the Gulf of Gabes, Hammamet and Tunis and it may diminish to 0 kg.h^{-1} . This variability can be explained by the effect of several factors such as spatio-temporal and environmental factors. This species can be fished throughout the year and the fishery is located on sand-muddy bottom. The bathymetric distribution of *Squilla mantis* ranges especially between 2 and 60m in the Tunisian Gulfs, with the highest abundance in depths shallower than 50m. From the analyses of the abundance data (Figs.9 and 10) it can be observed that *S. mantis* is abundant in the totality of the zones of the Gulf of Gabes. These areas, which are shallow with a wide platform and smooth slope provides an adequate habitat and soft bottomed habitat for this species. The cartography of the hourly yield shows that *Squilla mantis* is concentrated near the coast in the Gulf of Tunis (Fig. 12). This species is found in high densities in the west of the Gulf especially where the influence of river run-off is important (particularly Medjerda). The seasonal variation in the distribution of this species is very low in the Gulf of Tunis. For the Gulf of Hammamet, the most important indices

of abundance for this species are found in the region of Hergla, Jebel Hallouf and Kouria (Fig. 11). These areas are characterized by pits where *Penaeus kheraterus*, considered as the main food source for *S. mantis* (Mili et al., 2013), is abundant. The abundance indices of mantis shrimp in the Gulf of Hammamet are significantly lower than those in the Gulf of Gabes. The granulometry of the substrate has an influence on the presence and abundance of *Squilla mantis* due to its burrowing habits (Abelló and Sardà, 1989). The CPUE ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) of this species showed the typical coastal distribution on soft bottom up to 50-60m. *Squilla mantis* is a burrowing species, associated with littoral soft bottoms where sediment is silty sand to sandy mud and very poorly sorted (Atkinson et al., 1997).

Figure 9: Seasonal distribution and abundance of *Squilla mantis* in the Gulf of Gabes (2005).

Figure 10: Seasonal distribution and abundance of *Squilla mantis* in the Gulf of Gabes (2006).

Figure 11: Seasonal distribution and abundance of *Squilla mantis* in the Gulf of Hammamet.

Figure 12: Seasonal distribution and abundance of *Squilla mantis* in the Gulf of Tunis.

Effect of the special and environmental factors in the catches of *Squilla mantis*

To test the effect of several factors which can have an influence on the catches of *S. mantis*; we applied the test of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) one-way. All the factors tested such as season, hour, month, depth, weather and lunar cycle have a significant effect on the catches of this species using 95% confidence level in statistical inferences ($p < 0.05$). First, the special and environmental factors were tested separately one by one. Second, the

interaction effect between the variables was tested using two-way ANOVA using 95% confidence level in statistical inferences. According to this analysis, there is no interaction effect between these variables ($p > 0.05$).

Season

Seasonal variations in hourly yields result from reduced out-of-burrow activity because females rarely exit their burrow when they are incubating their eggs and their catch ability decreases especially in spring. The catch increases in autumn and winter with the highest values being in early summer due to the incorporation of new recruits (Fig.13). The changes of the concentration zones of *S. Mantis* is probably due to the transport of the pelagic larva from the shore to the large by the strong marine running in this area.

Figure 13: Effect of the season in CPUE of *Squilla mantis*.

Hour

Catches obtained during 24 hours show that the activity of the Mantis Shrimp peaks at night, between sunset and sunrise (Fig. 14). The maximum Catch per Unit Effort (CPUE) observed (6.6 kg/h) is between 3 o'clock and 6 o'clock AM when the Mantis Shrimps go to hide in burrows. The average values of the daily hourly yields range between 0.5-1kg/h, whereas the average values of the CPUE obtained at night are higher than 1kg/h. The burrowing behaviour of *Squilla mantis* makes it vulnerable to the bottom trawl only when individuals are out of their burrows. This behaviour makes this nychthemeral species less vulnerable to the fishery in day time trawling.

Figure 14: Effect of the hour in CPUE of *Squilla mantis*.

Month

Monthly catches show a remarkable seasonal variation with the highest values in late summer and early winter especially during July (average of the hourly yields more than 1.5kg/h), August and January (Fig. 15). The lowest catches occur from February (average of the hourly yields less than 0.5kg/h) to May because the adults disappear from the population after reproduction and the females do not exit their burrow incubating their eggs. The big variability of hauls (643) as well as their huge number causes an important Standard Deviation.

Figure 15: Effect of the month in CPUE of *Squilla mantis*.

Depth

Squilla mantis is found in the depth of around 2-60m, within the area intensively trawled (Fig. 16). The highest captures of *S. mantis* are observed in depths ranging between 20-28m and between 34-37m, corresponding to the pits of the Tunisian Gulfs. Except these depths where the average of the hourly yields is more than 1kg/h, the remaining depths show a CPUE less than 1kg/h. Our study proves that the typical depth interval for this species is 20-35m.

Figure 16: Effect of the depth in CPUE of *Squilla mantis*.

Weather

The weather has a big influence on the hourly yields of this species (Fig. 17). The values of average catches in bad weather (wind > 30 nautical miles per hour) (less than 0.5kg/h) is three times as higher as that in good weather (1.7kg/h). It can be explained by the destruction of the burrow or the difficulty for individuals to join their burrows because the turbulences in the sea-bed decrease the sight of this species. The maximum CPUE observed (6.6 kg/h) is recorded in bad weather (45NM/h).

Figure 17: Effect of the weather in CPUE of *Squilla mantis*.

Lunar cycle

The lunar cycle influences the catches of this species (Fig. 18). The hourly yields obtained at night show that the activity of the Mantis Shrimp peaks in full moon (average of the hourly yields 1.9kg/h). The moon light support the exit of this species outwards the burrow and makes it more vulnerable to the bottom trawl. The CPUE decreases in case of crescent or moon absence (average of the hourly yields less than 0.5kg/h). The same thing happens because of the darkening effect of the clouds in the sky.

Figure 18: Effect of the moon in CPUE of *Squilla mantis*.

DISCUSSION

Fisheries of *Squilla mantis* are found in the Mediterranean mostly in the vicinity of major rivers mouth: PO, Ebro, Rhone, and Nile (Maynou et al., 2005). The Mantis Shrimp is a benthic species, strongly related to bottom sediments as demonstrated by its burrowing behaviour and by the composition of its diet (Frogliia, 1996). The species also shows a territorial pattern of behaviour (Maynou et al., 2005). Information on burrowing behaviour of the species and its daily variation is found in Manfrin and Piccinetti (1970) and Atkinson et al. (1997). The burrowing behaviour of *Squilla mantis* makes it vulnerable to fishing gears if the animals are out of the burrows (Maynou et al., 2005). The bathymetric distribution of *S. mantis* is linked to muddy bottoms. The pattern of abundance with depth is similar to that found in the closely related species *Squilla empusa* in the Gulf of Mexico, which also prefers muddy areas (Abelló and Martín, 1993).

Catches obtained during one day with 24 sampling period by Frogliia and Giannini (1989) show that the activity of this species peaks at night especially at midnight. This behaviour makes the species less vulnerable to the fishery in areas where trawling is forbidden at night (Spanish waters) (Maynou et al., 2005).

According to Abelló and Martín (1993), there is no clear distribution pattern of size by depth, although they found that juveniles were more abundant in waters shallower than 30m depth. Piccinetti and Piccinetti-Manfrin, (1971) reported a certain variability in catches by depth and season, and suggested that temperature may play a role in determining Local migration of *S. mantis* in search of optimal temperature. This phenomenon has also been

reported by Do Chi (1978) and Lewinsohn and Manning (1980), but neither its importance to fisheries nor its causal mechanism have been thoroughly investigated. Seasonal variations in catchability result from reduced out-of-burrow activity, because females stay a long time and do not exit their burrow when they are incubating their egg mass (decreasing their catchability) in spring and early summer (Giovanardi and Piccinetti-Manfrin, 1984; Froglija, 1996). Additionally, catches also diminish in spring and summer because the adults disappear from the population after spawning (Abelló and Martín, 1993). Conversely, catches are much increased in winter, when mating takes place (Piccinetti and Piccinetti-Manfrin, 1971). Catches are further increased in late autumn (November-December) with the incorporation of new recruits (Abelló and Martín, 1993). In the Adriatic, the catch increases in autumn (November-December) also, as a by catch of the sole fishery (Piccinetti and Piccinetti-Manfrin, 1995). Additionally, weather and sea conditions represent an important influence on the catchability of this species (Maynou et al., 2005). Catches are reported to increase after prolonged bad weather condition in the Adriatic and in the Gulf of Gabes (after a strong sea storm), probably because of the disturbance of the burrow systems as a result of the high turbidity (Giovanardi and Piccinetti-Manfrin, 1984; Righini and Bairo, 1996, Mili et al., 2011).

The CPUE of commercial trawlers vary from <0.1 kg/h in summer to 1-2 kg/h in autumn (November-December) in the northern and central Adriatic (Piccinetti and Piccinetti-Manfrin, 1995). Values of up to 4 kg/h in autumn were reported by Manfrin et al. (1998) from the same area, increasing trend in the catches. *S. mantis* is found in depths of around 20-100m within the area intensively trawled (Abelló and Martín, 1993). Frequency of occurrence of *S.mantis* decreases with depth, this resource is most abundant at depth shallower than 60m (Maynou et al., 2005). Maximum hourly yields are obtained shallower than 20m depth (more than 4kg/h) and yield decreases sharply at depths beyond 60m, the deepest distribution bathymetry is at 100-120m (Abelló and Martín, 1993). The preferential stratum (10-50 m) and order of magnitude of abundances indexes from about 1 kg.km⁻² up to 6 kg.km⁻² are reported for MEDITS (Mediterranean International Trawl Surveys) experimental bottom trawl surveys, which are carried out using an *ad hoc*-developed gear with a performance for *S. mantis* not significantly different from the commercial gear (Maynou et al., 2005). Density-dependent phenomena is relate to controversial and often confounding (given the difficulty to discriminate density dependence from environmental influence) responses of the stock dynamics to its own density (Ragonese et al., 2012).

Additionally, the analyses of stomach contents provided evidence of a significant increase in the percentage of empty stomachs at day-time and a diel feeding rhythm, clearly related with *S. mantis* night peaks of activity and also catchability (Mili et al., 2013). The main food items recorded in stomachs analyzed, by many authors working in *Squilla mantis* in the Mediterranean Sea, were crustaceans, mollusks, and fishes, with a high percentage of empty stomach and a strong seasonal variability in prey types (Maynou et al., 2005). As already pointed out by Piccinetti-Manfrin (1999) this species may be an opportunistic predator and its diet reflects the local availability of food. Demestre et al. (2000) found that the mantis shrimp tends to aggregate with increasing trawl disturbance and is an opportunistic scavenger that feeds on dead animals after the passage of the trawl. All these observations confirm that this species is associated to benthic fishes and especially crustacean representing the main food for *S. mantis*.

The fishery for *S. mantis* is not specifically regulated. It belongs to the general multi-species trawl fishery practiced on continental shelves in the Mediterranean (Maynou et al., 2005) with seasonal changes of target species. The most important co-occurring species are the shrimp *Melicertus kerathurus*, the sole *Solea solea*, the cuttlefish *Sepia officinalis*, and the red mullets *Mullus spp.* (Abelló and Martín, 1993). The fact that egg-bearing females do not exit their burrow during incubation, the relatedness of the catchability to period of the day and weather conditions stand for the important factors which protect the species from fishing pressure. Additionally, the upper 50m (or inner 3 miles from shore) of the continental shelf are closed to trawl fishing in the Mediterranean (Maynou et al., 2005), thus protecting a significant part of the depth range of this species. Conversely, the use of heavy trawling gear, which damages the muddy bottom where *Squilla mantis* lives, can be a negative factor which hinders the conservation of this species. For a better management of *Squilla mantis* fisheries it is important to improve the information data base on this species (catches and landings, effort, prices), to study the impact caused by the trawl fishery, and monitoring abundance and population parameters.

REFERENCES

- Abelló, P. and Martín, P. 1993. Fishery dynamics of the mantis shrimp *Squilla mantis* (Crustacea: Decapoda) population off the Ebro Delta (northwestern Mediterranean). Fish. Res., 16: 131-145.
- Abelló, P. and Sardá, F. 1989. Some observations on the biology and fishery of *Squilla mantis* L. in the Catalan area (NW Mediterranean). In: E. A. Ferrero (ed.), Biology of Stomatopods: 229-239. (Mucchi Ed., Modena).
- Atkinson, R. J. A., Froglija, C., Arneri, E. and Antolini, B. 1997. Observation on the burrows and burrowing behaviour of *Squilla mantis* (L.) (Crustacea: Stomatopoda). Mar. Ecol., 18 (4): 337-359.
- Demestre, M., Sanchez, P. and Kaiser, M.J. 2000. The behavioral response of benthic scavengers to otter trawling disturbance in the Mediterranean. In: Effects of fishing on non-target species and habitats (M. J. Kaiser & S.J. De Groot eds), Blackwell Science: Oxford. 121 - 129.

- Do Chi, T. 1978. Modèles cinétiques et structuraux en dynamique des populations exploitées. Application aux squilles, *Squilla mantis* (L.) (Crustacé Stomatopode) du Golfe du Lion. Ph. D. Thesis, Université de Montpellier, 380 pp.
- Frogliola, C. 1996. Growth and behaviour of *Squilla mantis* (mantis shrimp) in the Adriatic Sea. Final Report. EU Study DG XIV/MED/93/016.
- Frogliola, C. and Giannini, S. 1989. Field observations on diel rhythms in catchability and feeding of *Squilla mantis* (Crustacea, Stomatopoda) in the Adriatic Sea. In: E. A. Ferrero (ed.), Biology of Stomatopods: 87- 97. (Mucchi Ed., Modena).
- Giovanardi, C. and Piccinetti-Manfrin, G. 1984. Summary of biological parameters of *Squilla mantis* L. in the Adriatic Sea. FAO Fish. Rep., 290:131-134.
- Lewinsohn, C. and Manning, R. B., 1980. Stomatopod Crustacea from the eastern Mediterranean. Smithsonian Contr. to Zool., 305: 1-22
- M'Rabet, R. 1995. Les engins de pêche les plus utilisés dans les eaux tunisiennes et les effets néfastes causés par certains engins sur les ressources halieutiques. Rapp. Doc. INSTOP, 1-1995 :13p.
- Manfrin G., and Piccinetti, C. 1970. Osservazioni etologiche su *Squilla mantis* L. Note Lab. Biol. Mar. E Pesca, Fano, 3 (5): 93-104.
- Manfrin, G., Paolini, M. and Piccinetti, C. 1998. Le risorse demersali dell'alto e medio Adriatico. Biol. Mar. Mediterranea, 5 (3): 96-108.
- Maynou, F., Abelló, P. and Sartor, P. 2005. A review of the fisheries biology of the mantis shrimp, *Squilla mantis* (L., 1758) (Stomatopoda, Squillidae) in the Mediterranean. Crustaceana, 77(9): 1081-1099.
- Mili, S., Jaroui, O. et Missaoui, H. 2008. Caractères biométriques de la squille *Squilla mantis* dans les eaux tunisiennes. Bull. Inst. Natn. Tech. Mer de Salammbô, 35: 1-14.
- Mili, S., Missaoui, H. and Jarboui O. 2011. Distribution and effect of the special and environmental factors in the catches of the mantis shrimp *Squilla mantis* (Crustacea: Stomatopoda) in the gulf of Gabes (Tunisia). Egypt J. Aquat. Biol. & Fish, 15 (1): 157 -171.
- Mili, S., Bouriga, N., Ennouri, R., Jarboui, O. and Missaoui, H. 2013. Food and biochemical composition of the spot-tail mantis shrimp *Squilla mantis* caught in three Tunisian Gulfs: Tunis, Hammamet and Gabes. Cah. Biol. Mar., 54: 271-280.
- Piccinetti, C. and Piccinetti-Manfrin, G. 1971. Osservazioni sulla pesca di *Squilla mantis* L. Note Lab. Biol. Mar. E Pesca, fano, 4 (2): 25-403.
- Piccinetti, C. and Piccinetti-Manfrin, G. 1995. Considerazione sulla stato di sfruttamento delle risorse demersali (alto e medio Adriatico). Biol. Mar. Mediterranea, 1 (2): 77-87.
- Piccinetti-Manfrin, G. 1999. *Squilla mantis*. Biolo. Mar. Med., 6 (1): 499-502.
- Ragonese, S., Morara, U., Canali, E., Pagliarino E. and Bianchini, M.L. 2012. Abundance and biological traits of the spottail mantis shrimp, *Squilla mantis* (L., 1758) (Crustacea: Stomatopoda), off the southern coast of Sicily. Cah. de Biol. Mar., 53: 485-493.
- Righini, P. and Baino, R. 1996. Parametri popolazionistici della pannocchia (*Squilla mantis*, Crustacea: Stomatopoda). Biol. Mar. Mediterranea, 3 (1): 565-566.
- Zar, J. H. 1984. Biostatistical Analyses. Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliff.